

“Realities in the translation of "Boburnoma" into foreign languages”

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Abstract: *In this article, "Boburnoma" is translated into different foreign languages, "Boburnoma" depicts a large number of historical figures, their mental state changes quickly in a changing and unstable political environment, and from a state of mental defeat. secondly, issues such as returning to the winning position and having to suffer the bitter pain of defeat again in an instant are highlighted.*

Key words: *"Boburnoma", foreign languages, objective assessment, artistic image, Uzbek literature, science, encyclopedic source, mental state.*

Babur Mirza, the descendant of Amir Temur, a sensitive poet, an encyclopedist, a famous statesman and a skilled general, left a unique and rich creative-scientific heritage. Undoubtedly, the masterpiece of Babur's work is the historical-biographical work "Boburnoma", which tells about the historical events that took place in Central Asia, Afghanistan, India and Iran in the 15th-16th centuries. This memory book, skillfully arranged on the basis of extremely important and multifaceted information, can be compared to an incomparable living encyclopedia in terms of content. "Boburnoma" reflects ancient values, intellectual and spiritual treasures of our people like a mirror.

This publication was born as an effective and bright example of literary, cultural and humanitarian cooperation between the Uzbek and Italian peoples. The book opens with the Foreword of the head of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoyev. It is known

that "Boburnoma" has attracted the attention of Eastern and Western researchers in various scientific fields for many centuries. This rare book, which has been translated into many languages of the world, is now available to Italian readers for the first time.

A large group of qualified translators, editors and designers led by the head of this publishing house, Sandro Teti, was involved in the process of publishing the work in Italian. Rector of Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature named after Alisher Navoi, professor Shuhrat Sirojiddinov and famous Italian Turkologist, professor Federico De Renzi participated in the preparation of the book as scientific and literary editors.

In the introduction to the work "Baburnoma" written by the famous Italian scientist and writer Franco Cardini, Babur is described as "a great ruler who loved the art of words or a great writer who loved the kingdom". A European reader who decides to read "Boburnoma" will definitely not be able to resist it. At the same time, humanist pope Pius II - "Comments" of Enea Silvio Piccolomini, autobiographical comments of Emperor Peter Leopold Habsburg come to mind involuntarily; sometimes the reader feels like reading Montaigne, and sometimes Marco Polo or Frederick the Great or Melville," says Cardini.

The translator Federico Pastore, in his review of the book, emphasizes that "Boburnoma" is "the first true example of an autobiographical work typical of Islamic civilization, which allows us to reconstruct the daily life of its time." The Italian translation of the work is based on the English translation by Wheeler M. Thaxton. and he preserved all the characteristics of Babur Mirzo's memoirs as much as possible and completely, "zero, the integrity of the memories clearly reflects the bright image of one of the main heroes of the history of Asia of the 16th century." This edition is decorated with 96 artistic miniatures from the Babur period. These pictures were an

advanced direction of painting that revealed the characters and inner world of the characters of the book in a real, realistic way, fully taking into account the historical, geographical, etymological factors for that time. The famous miraculous paintings are distinguished by their color palette, elegant decoration and deep meaning. The book "Boburnoma" published in many copies is presented to many book centers in Italy and Europe. Below, the famous Italian scientist and writer Franco Cardini's essay on "Boburnoma" is published with partial reductions.

We, the "people of the West", owe the culture of other peoples of the world an enormous debt: we invaded other people's lands, looted their property, and subjugated them to us. Even the Roman law that we created, despite being read over and over again and introduced through Christian teaching, is known to allow us to act like conquerors, murderers, and slavers. In this regard, it is necessary to emphasize one fact that does not require proof: we have had crueller actions than seizing the wealth of other nations, depriving them of their freedom and life. That is, it is not a secret that we despised non-nationals and peoples because they thought differently from us and looked at them as an "inferior" class.

They did not have the weapons and sometimes even the desire to resist our oppression. We have never disrespected the values of other nations in terms of science, art, and beauty, not even recently. We were only interested in acquiring their material wealth. We even invented the false concept of "nations without history" to cover up our crimes faster and justify ourselves. However, the riches that we forcibly took from these nations were actually only a superficial, external part of their real, original and extremely incalculable treasures. Therefore, even when we later began to appreciate these spiritual treasures, we approached this issue with the spirit of colonialism or, according to our mistaken imagination, as anthropologists who

considered their knowledge superior to theirs. , we regretfully admit that if we had studied and understood the way of life and thinking of other peoples in time, we would have protected ourselves not only from the evil of criminal acts and abuse, but also from all obstacles and in this day and age, when ghouls have lost their essence (although we still have unpleasant memories of our past injustices), we would find it easier to live with them.

We also changed our concepts and ideas about the past and the future - we accepted the reality of exoticism and orientalism in its entirety. Moreover, during our historical journey since the 18th century, we fell in love with this civilization, these traditions, these sights, these sounds, and even smells and tastes, to justify ourselves. As old as the world itself, this deed reminds us of the fate of the conqueror who ends up falling in love with his beautiful victim. But sometimes we openly admit that we are imperfect. The development of scientific and technical discoveries has changed our perceptions and attitudes for thousands of years, not only in the field of trade, but also in scientific, cultural, aesthetic and ethical fields. Only now, with a delay of centuries, we accept this miracle as if it were familiar to us from before, and now we are facing "other peoples" and our communication with them is giving positive results.

For example, when we look back at the glory and luxury of India during the time of the Great Mongols or more precisely, the Babur dynasty, we look at the beauty of these cities, palaces and gardens, and the Uyg created at the peak of our cultural development. We see the "other Renaissance" equal to the achievements of the Renaissance period, and in some places even more than them. We can only say for our own comfort that these people could have taught us anger, cruelty, greed and deceit.

Zahir al-Din Muhammad is a great person known at the same time as Babur (Babur is a Muslim noble name that means babr in Persian, i.e. "tiger", just like Timur's name means "iron"). His life and work can be a wonderful and bright example of the Turanian culture, which was formed in the vast expanses between the Caspian Sea, Hindikush and Tianshan mountains, occupied by the Orol-Altai tribes, which are the ancient treasure of Iranians.

Over time, the Turkic peoples to which Babur belonged managed to build a common culture with the Iranians, despite the thousands of differences between them, and worked linguistically within the framework of the Turkish-Iranian-Arabic "triad". That is, during their lives, they alternately used the Arabic language, which sometimes talks about Allah and with Allah, sometimes the Persian language, which expresses love and happiness, and sometimes the Turkish language, which shows military potential and fighting power they came.

Babur was born in February 1483 in Andijan, an ancient city located on one of the branches of the Silk Road. This city is located between Koshgar in China's Xinjiang region, Osh in Kyrgyzstan and Kokan in Fergana valley, in today's Uzbekistan. Babur is the great-grandson of Amir Temur, the legendary ruler of Samarkand, and the eldest son of Qutlugh Nigorkhanim, a noble princess who is a distant descendant of Genghis Khan. He spoke the old Uzbek language, but he also knew the Persian language, which is common to all of Central Asia, and, of course, the Arabic language for reciting, understanding and interpreting the Qur'an. Babur's followers and his army were ethnically diverse.

"Boburnoma", a rare example of world and Uzbek literature, is also important as an encyclopedic resource that provides information on many fields of science. The translation of "Boburnoma" into several foreign languages, as well as the research

conducted by foreign scientists on it, also indicate how unique the work is. revealed in detail the artistic representation of the mental states of victory and defeat. Babur's activity as an expert who was able to objectively evaluate the era and historical figures, the situation where the essence of the subject happened in the fate of one person is highlighted. In particular, the analysis of the image of victory and defeat in the "Boburnoma" in the mentality of the rulers of the time through clear and reasonable examples is the basis of the dissertation. is the most culminating point.

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